

Exact general solution of the Schrödinger equation by modified Cole-Hopf transformation

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Abstract

The Schrödinger equation is a linear partial differential equation that describes the temporal evolution of the state of a quantum mechanical system. One of the pillars of quantum mechanics, the Schrödinger equation has been used to describe a wide variety of phenomena such as wave-particle duality, atomic orbitals, quantum oscillations, and even some fluid mechanics problems. Despite its established importance in the development of quantum mechanics, a solution of the Schrödinger equation for an arbitrary distribution of quantum mechanical potential or for an arbitrary number of space dimensions remains unknown. This work seeks to rectify this theoretical roadblock by providing an analytical solution through a recasting of the well-known Cole-Hopf transformation which is used to linearize a broad class of PDEs of which the Schrödinger equation becomes a member after an earlier change of variables. These two successive transformations render the general wave function proportional to the solution of a forced heat equation, allowing an explicit analytical solution applicable to any system in any number of space dimensions. Two practical applications to deriving the explicit wave functions of multielectronic atoms and to the forced Burgers equation of fluid mechanics are discussed, enabling greater mathematical insight into quantum entanglement and nonlinear fluid systems.

1 Introduction

Consider a particle of mass $m \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ surrounded by a temporally evolving region of n -dimensional Euclidean space $\Omega : t \in \mathbb{R} \rightarrow S \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$. The Schrödinger equation [1] on Ω is given by (1), whose solution $\Psi : (\mathbf{r} \in \Omega(t) \times t \in \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ is the wave function of the particle given a potential $V : (\mathbf{r} \in \Omega \times t \in \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ and the reduced Planck constant $\hbar = \frac{6.62607015 \times 10^{-34}}{2\pi}$ J · s.

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \Psi(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} = V(\mathbf{r}, t)\Psi - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 \Psi(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (1)$$

Despite (1) belonging to the well-studied category of linear second-order partial differential equations (PDEs) and a century of research on the systems it describes, its general solution for arbitrary $V(\mathbf{r}, t)$ remains unknown. This is largely due to the fact that there exists no sufficiently general and widely known method of analytically solving second-order PDEs with variable coefficients. Describing practically significant cases which almost always include more than one particle or atomic orbital requires one to solve (1) in contexts of increasingly complicated expressions of $V(\mathbf{r}, t)$ due to nonlinear feedback effects between the various particles or other bodies being modeled. Multi-body problems similar to those encountered in celestial mechanics are common when studying heavier

atoms, starting with the helium atom's two electrons generating a rather discouraging instance of the notorious three-body problem. The analytical solution proposed in this work (Claim 1) uses a change of variables to transform (1) into an equation of the same class as that which the Cole-Hopf transform [2] [3] was originally formulated to solve, albeit with a forcing term equaling $V(\mathbf{r}, t)$. The first transformation is well-known for transforming the Riccati equation into a Sturm-Liouville problem [4], and its result when applied here being a Cole-Hopf equation implies that (1) may be reduced to a heat equation with constant coefficients via a modified Cole-Hopf transform. The Cole-Hopf transform has previously enjoyed success in solving the viscous Burgers equation in fluid mechanics. Since heat equations have unique and bounded analytical solutions and the exponential function of the Riccati-Sturm-Liouville transformation is smooth and continuous, a fairly robust solution to (1) could be recovered by reversing both changes of variables.

Claim 1 *There exists an analytical solution $\Psi : (\mathbf{r} \in \Omega(t) \times t \in \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ of (1) given a sufficiently smooth Dirichlet boundary condition $\Psi_\Omega : (\mathbf{r} \in \partial\Omega(t) \times t \in \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, a sufficiently smooth initial condition $\Psi_0 : \mathbf{r} \in \Omega(0) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, and a normalization condition $N : t \in \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$.*

Such a solution is expected to have broad impact in quantum mechanics since (1) is one of the pillars of the aforementioned field. Applications in cosmology are expected, possibly reaching into the more general area of quantum field theory (QFT) which is in need of a formal mathematical foundation. Part of the reason for the formal unfoundedness of QFT is that our understanding of quantum wave function behavior in multiparticle systems remains in its infancy. This solution is of the kind that will enable deeper research on this matter. QFT is also of cosmological interest in its own right since one of the most plausible non-string theoretical pathways to a "theory of everything" is widely considered as first setting QFT on a formal mathematical foundation, and then adapting said theory to curved Lorentzian spacetime, and finally reconciling its peculiarities with those of general relativity so as to produce a smooth fit to measured cosmological parameters. Rich applications in quantum computing are expected since qubit cores are another class of multiparticle quantum systems in need of study by reason of their lucrative practical applications.

2 Literary review

Solutions of (1) are scarce in the literature. The solutions that are known are usually for very specific situations with little practical applications, called "toy models" by some, since they can only describe one particle at a time and thus neglect the effects of quantum entanglement [5]. The most groundbreaking solution from a theoretical physics standpoint thus far is most likely that which was discovered by Schrödinger himself: the wave function yielding the probability of locating the lone electron inhabiting a hydrogen atom [6]. Despite the simplicity of hydrogen atoms in light of the complexity of heavier elements, the wave functions of their electron clouds contain much less simple mathematical constructs such as generalized Laguerre polynomials and Gegenbauer polynomials along with spherical harmonics which are cemented together by the principal, azimuthal, and magnetic quantum numbers associated with their electrons. Some cases of higher orbitals in hydrogen-like atoms have also been found and are widely taught in university lectures on chemistry, forming the basis of almost all course material regarding orbitals. However, a complete wave function for the helium atom or for any heavier atoms has not yet been found due to the complexity of $V(\mathbf{r}, t)$ transcending known mathematical methods. Other solutions have been found in the form of harmonic oscillators [7] used to demonstrate wave-particle duality.

3 Proof of Claim 1

3.1 Reduction to Cole-Hopf form

Substituting the Riccati-Sturm-Liouville transformation $\Psi(\mathbf{r}, t) = e^{\phi(\mathbf{r}, t)}$ into (1) separates the Laplacian in (1) into the sum of the Laplacian applied to the unknown $\phi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ and the squared L^2 -norm of the gradient of the unknown (2).

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} e^{\phi(\mathbf{r}, t)} = V(\mathbf{r}, t) e^{\phi(\mathbf{r}, t)} - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 \phi(\mathbf{r}, t) e^{\phi(\mathbf{r}, t)} - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \|\nabla \phi(\mathbf{r}, t)\|^2 e^{\phi(\mathbf{r}, t)} \quad (2)$$

Dividing (2) by $i\hbar e^{\phi(\mathbf{r}, t)}$ yields an inhomogeneous version (3) of the PDE used in the original proof of the Cole-Hopf transform, which is used to solve the class of quadratically nonlinear PDEs which possess a first time derivative, a Laplacian operator, and a squared L^2 -norm of the gradient operator all applied to the unknown.

$$\frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{V(\mathbf{r}, t)}{i\hbar} + \frac{i\hbar}{2m} \nabla^2 \phi(\mathbf{r}, t) + \frac{i\hbar}{2m} \|\nabla \phi(\mathbf{r}, t)\|^2 \quad (3)$$

3.2 Reduction to forced heat equation by Cole-Hopf transform

The quadratically nonlinear PDE (3) must be converted to a form whose solution is known in order to proceed. The Cole-Hopf transformation was originally designed to solve PDEs equaling the homogeneous version of (3) by transforming them into unforced linear heat equations. Due to the linearity of the operations involved in deriving the Cole-Hopf transformation, it is reasonable to expect that attempting the same derivation process for the inhomogeneous version (3) of the Cole-Hopf equation would result in some type of heat equation (Claim 2).

Claim 2 *Let $g \in \{\Psi, \phi, V\} : (\mathbf{r} \in \Omega(t) \times t \in \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ and $(a, b) \subseteq \mathbb{C}^2$. Then, there exists a change of variables $\Theta : \phi(\mathbf{r}, t) \rightarrow \Phi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ from the inhomogeneous Cole-Hopf equation $\frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} = V(\mathbf{r}, t) + a \nabla^2 \phi(\mathbf{r}, t) + b \|\nabla \phi(\mathbf{r}, t)\|^2$ to a heat equation $\frac{\partial \Phi(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} = f(\Phi(\mathbf{r}, t), \mathbf{r}, t) + b \nabla^2 \Phi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ given sufficiently smooth boundary conditions $g_\Omega : (\mathbf{r} \in \partial\Omega(t) \times t \in \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ and initial conditions $g_0 : \mathbf{r} \in \Omega(0) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, where f is a function to be determined.*

3.2.1 Proof of Claim 2

Let there exist a composite function $\Theta : \phi(\mathbf{r}, t) \rightarrow \Phi(\mathbf{r}, t)$. Then, the time derivative and Laplacian of $\Phi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ are given by (4).

$$\frac{\partial \Phi(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial \Theta(\phi(\mathbf{r}, t))}{\partial \phi(\mathbf{r}, t)} \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t}, \quad \nabla^2 \Phi(\mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{\partial \Theta(\phi(\mathbf{r}, t))}{\partial \phi(\mathbf{r}, t)} \nabla^2 \phi(\mathbf{r}, t) + \frac{\partial^2 \Theta(\phi(\mathbf{r}, t))}{\partial \phi(\mathbf{r}, t)^2} \|\nabla \phi(\mathbf{r}, t)\|^2 \quad (4)$$

Multiplying both sides of (3) by $\frac{\partial \Theta(\phi(\mathbf{r}, t))}{\partial \phi(\mathbf{r}, t)}$ equates the result with the definition of $\frac{\partial \Phi(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t}$, yielding (5).

$$\frac{\partial \Phi(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial \Theta(\phi(\mathbf{r}, t))}{\partial \phi(\mathbf{r}, t)} \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial \Theta(\phi(\mathbf{r}, t))}{\partial \phi(\mathbf{r}, t)} \left(\frac{V(\mathbf{r}, t)}{i\hbar} + \frac{i\hbar}{2m} \nabla^2 \phi(\mathbf{r}, t) + \frac{i\hbar}{2m} \|\nabla \phi(\mathbf{r}, t)\|^2 \right) \quad (5)$$

Solving (4) for $\frac{\partial\Theta(\phi(\mathbf{r},t))}{\partial\phi(\mathbf{r},t)}\nabla^2\phi(\mathbf{r},t)$ and substituting the result (6) into (5) yields (7).

$$\frac{\partial\Theta(\phi(\mathbf{r},t))}{\partial\phi(\mathbf{r},t)}\nabla^2\phi(\mathbf{r},t) = \nabla^2\Phi(\mathbf{r},t) - \frac{\partial^2\Theta(\phi(\mathbf{r},t))}{\partial\phi(\mathbf{r},t)^2}\|\nabla\phi(\mathbf{r},t)\|^2 \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial\Phi(\mathbf{r},t)}{\partial t} &= \frac{\partial\Theta(\phi(\mathbf{r},t))}{\partial\phi(\mathbf{r},t)}\frac{V(\mathbf{r},t)}{i\hbar} + \frac{i\hbar}{2m}\left(\nabla\Phi(\mathbf{r},t) - \frac{\partial^2\Theta(\phi(\mathbf{r},t))}{\partial\phi(\mathbf{r},t)^2}\|\nabla\phi(\mathbf{r},t)\|^2\right) + \\ &\quad \frac{i\hbar}{2m}\frac{\partial\Theta(\phi(\mathbf{r},t))}{\partial\phi(\mathbf{r},t)}\|\nabla\phi(\mathbf{r},t)\|^2 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Combining like terms of (7) involving the squared L^2 -norm of $\phi(\mathbf{r},t)$ results in (8). $\Theta(\phi(\mathbf{r},t))$ must then be chosen such that both $\frac{\partial^2\Theta(\phi(\mathbf{r},t))}{\partial\phi(\mathbf{r},t)^2} + \frac{\partial\Theta(\phi(\mathbf{r},t))}{\partial\phi(\mathbf{r},t)} = 0$ and $\frac{\partial\Theta(\phi(\mathbf{r},t))}{\partial\phi(\mathbf{r},t)} = \frac{i\hbar}{V(\mathbf{r},t)}$ in order for (8) to reduce to a forced heat equation in $\Phi(\mathbf{r},t)$. If at least one of these two conditions fails to be met, the modified Cole-Hopf transformation fails and the argument for solution to (1) follows suit.

$$\frac{\partial\Phi(\mathbf{r},t)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial\Theta(\phi(\mathbf{r},t))}{\partial\phi(\mathbf{r},t)}\frac{V(\mathbf{r},t)}{i\hbar} + \frac{i\hbar}{2m}\nabla^2\Phi(\mathbf{r},t) + \frac{i\hbar}{2m}\left(\frac{\partial\Theta(\phi(\mathbf{r},t))}{\partial\phi(\mathbf{r},t)} - \frac{\partial^2\Theta(\phi(\mathbf{r},t))}{\partial\phi(\mathbf{r},t)^2}\right)\|\nabla\phi(\mathbf{r},t)\|^2 \quad (8)$$

To find $\Theta(\phi(\mathbf{r},t))$, the second condition for reduction of (8) to a heat equation is substituted (9) into the first and the result integrated twice (10). Since arbitrary constants of integration are generally disregarded when deriving a change of variables, putting $C_0 = C_1 = 0$ yields the invertible formula (10) mapping (3) to a forced heat equation (11). Claim 2 is proven with $f = 1$. The result is contained within Theorem 1.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2\Theta(\phi(\mathbf{r},t))}{\partial\phi(\mathbf{r},t)^2} &= \frac{\partial\Theta(\phi(\mathbf{r},t))}{\partial\phi(\mathbf{r},t)} \wedge \frac{\partial\Theta(\phi(\mathbf{r},t))}{\partial\phi(\mathbf{r},t)} = \frac{i\hbar}{V(\mathbf{r},t)} \implies \frac{\partial^2\Theta(\phi(\mathbf{r},t))}{\partial\phi(\mathbf{r},t)^2} = \frac{i\hbar}{V(\mathbf{r},t)} \\ \implies \Theta(\phi(\mathbf{r},t)) &= \iint \frac{i\hbar}{V(\mathbf{r},t)} d\phi(\mathbf{r},t)^2 = \frac{i\hbar\phi^2(\mathbf{r},t)}{2V(\mathbf{r},t)} + C_0\phi(\mathbf{r},t) + C_1 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

$$\Phi(\mathbf{r},t) = \Theta(\phi(\mathbf{r},t)) = \frac{i\hbar\phi^2(\mathbf{r},t)}{2V(\mathbf{r},t)} \implies \phi(\mathbf{r},t) = \sqrt{\frac{2\Phi(\mathbf{r},t)V(\mathbf{r},t)}{i\hbar}} \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{\partial\Phi(\mathbf{r},t)}{\partial t} = 1 + \frac{i\hbar}{2m}\nabla^2\Phi(\mathbf{r},t) \quad (11)$$

Theorem 1 Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $\Omega : t \in \mathbb{R} \rightarrow S \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$, $g \in \{\phi, \Phi, V\} : (\mathbf{r} \in \Omega \times t \in \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, and $(a, b) \in \mathbb{C}^2$. Then, the invertible change of variables $\phi(\mathbf{r},t) = \sqrt{\frac{2\Phi(\mathbf{r},t)V(\mathbf{r},t)}{i\hbar}}$ maps the inhomogeneous Cole-Hopf equation $\frac{\partial\phi(\mathbf{r},t)}{\partial t} = V(\mathbf{r},t) + a\nabla^2\phi(\mathbf{r},t) + b\|\nabla\phi(\mathbf{r},t)\|^2$ to the unit-forced heat equation $\frac{\partial\Phi(\mathbf{r},t)}{\partial t} = 1 + b\nabla^2\Phi(\mathbf{r},t)$ in n space dimensions and time, given sufficiently smooth boundary conditions $g_\Omega : (\mathbf{r} \in \partial\Omega(t) \times t \in \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ and initial conditions $g_0 : \mathbf{r} \in \Omega(0) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$.

3.3 Solving the forced heat equation

The analytical solution (12) of (11) is well-studied on both bounded [8] and unbounded [9] domains. For the bounded case, $G : (\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') \in \mathbb{R}^{2n} \times t \in \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ is the Green's function associated with the geometry of $\Omega(t)$ and $\hat{N}_{\mathbf{r}'}$ is the unit outward normal vector on $\partial\Omega(t)$. $\Phi_0 : \mathbf{r} \in \Omega(0) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ is the initial condition while $\Phi_\Omega : (\mathbf{r} \in \partial\Omega(t) \times t \in \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ is the boundary condition.

$$\Phi(\mathbf{r}, t) = \begin{cases} \Phi_{\text{bounded}}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \int_{\Omega(t)} \Phi_0(\mathbf{r}') G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', t) d\mathbf{r}' - \int_0^t \int_{\Omega(t)} G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', t - \tau) d\mathbf{r}' d\tau + \\ \frac{i\hbar}{2m} \int_0^t \oint_{\partial\Omega(t)} \Phi_\Omega(\mathbf{r}', \tau) \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', t - \tau)}{\partial \hat{N}_{\mathbf{r}'}} d\mathbf{r}' d\tau \\ \Phi_{\text{unbounded}}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{1}{\left(2\sqrt{\frac{\pi i \hbar t}{2m}}\right)^n} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \Phi_0(\mathbf{r}') \exp\left(-\frac{m|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|^2}{2i\hbar t}\right) d\mathbf{r}' + \\ \int_0^t \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{m|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|^2}{2i\hbar(t - \tau)}\right)}{\left(2\sqrt{\frac{\pi i \hbar(t - \tau)}{2m}}\right)^n} d\mathbf{r}' d\tau \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

3.4 Constructing the wave function

Reversing the two changes of variables that gave rise to (11) from (3) and to (3) from (1) allows the wave function to be recovered (13) along with the initial and boundary conditions (14).

$$\Psi(\mathbf{r}, t) = \exp\left(\sqrt{\frac{2\Phi(\mathbf{r}, t)V(\mathbf{r}, t)}{i\hbar}}\right) \quad (13)$$

$$\Phi_0(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{i\hbar}{2V_0(\mathbf{r})} \ln^2(\Psi_0(\mathbf{r})), \quad \Phi_\Omega(\mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{i\hbar}{2V_\Omega(\mathbf{r}, t)} \ln^2(\Psi_\Omega(\mathbf{r}, t)) \quad (14)$$

Substituting (14) into (12) and the result into (13) fully specifies the general wave function (15) in terms of its boundary and initial conditions. (15) is the general solution of (1) in any number n of spatial dimensions on a bounded domain $\Omega \subseteq (\mathbb{R}^n \times t \in \mathbb{R})$ or on an unbounded domain $\mathbb{R}^n \times t \in \mathbb{R}$.

$$\Psi(\mathbf{r}, t) = \begin{cases} \Psi_{\text{bounded}}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \exp\left(\left(\left(V(\mathbf{r}, t) \int_{\Omega(t)} \frac{\ln^2(\Psi_0(\mathbf{r}'))}{V_0(\mathbf{r}')} G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', t) d\mathbf{r}' - \frac{2V(\mathbf{r}, t)}{i\hbar} \int_0^t \int_{\Omega(t)} G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', t - \tau) d\mathbf{r}' d\tau + \frac{i\hbar V(\mathbf{r}, t)}{2m} \int_0^t \oint_{\partial\Omega(t)} \frac{\ln^2(\Psi_\Omega(\mathbf{r}', \tau))}{V_\Omega(\mathbf{r}', \tau)} \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', t - \tau)}{\partial \hat{N}_{\mathbf{r}'}} d\mathbf{r}' d\tau\right)^{1/2}\right)\right) \\ \Psi_{\text{unbounded}}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \exp\left(\left(\left(\frac{2V(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\left(2\sqrt{\frac{\pi i \hbar t}{2m}}\right)^n} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{\ln^2(\Psi_0(\mathbf{r}'))}{2V_0(\mathbf{r}')} \exp\left(-\frac{m|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|^2}{2i\hbar t}\right) d\mathbf{r}' + \frac{2V(\mathbf{r}, t)}{i\hbar} \int_0^t \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{m|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|^2}{2i\hbar(t - \tau)}\right)}{\left(2\sqrt{\frac{\pi i \hbar(t - \tau)}{2m}}\right)^n} d\mathbf{r}' d\tau\right)^{1/2}\right)\right) \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

3.4.1 Extension to the time-independent Schrödinger equation

The time-independent Schrödinger equation (16) is used to model systems whose wave functions need not evolve through time. It is clear that the Riccati-Sturm-Liouville transform (1-3) and the

subsequent modified Cole-Hopf transform (3-11) which both transform the Schrödinger equation (1) into the forced heat equation (11) hold when $\frac{\partial \Psi(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} = 0 \implies \Psi : \mathbf{r} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$. The forced heat equation becomes a Poisson equation (17) with constant source term, whose solution is well-known for both bounded [10] and unbounded [11] domains. The quantity $\frac{\partial G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')}{\partial \hat{N}_{\mathbf{r}'}}$ represents the derivative of the Green's function associated with Ω taken with respect to the unit outward normal vector $\hat{N}$ of $\partial\Omega$ as measured by the variable of integration $\mathbf{r}'$ while $\Gamma(n/2)$ denotes the gamma function of $n/2$. Substitution of the Poisson solution (17) into the inverse transformations (13-14) yielding the wave function and its boundary conditions results in the solution (18) to (16).

$$\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 \Psi(\mathbf{r}) = V(\mathbf{r}) \Psi(\mathbf{r}) \quad (16)$$

$$\nabla^2 \Phi(\mathbf{r}) = -\frac{2m}{\hbar^2} \implies \begin{cases} \Phi_{\text{bounded}}(\mathbf{r}) = -\frac{m\Gamma(n/2)}{\hbar^2(n-2)\sqrt{\pi^n}} \int_{\Omega(t)} G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r}' - \oint_{\partial\Omega(t)} \Phi_{\Omega}(\mathbf{r}) \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')}{\partial \hat{N}_{\mathbf{r}'}} d\mathbf{r}' \\ \Phi_{\text{unbounded}}(\mathbf{r}) = -\frac{m\Gamma(n/2)}{\hbar^2(n-2)\sqrt{\pi^n}} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{d\mathbf{r}'}{|\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}'|^{n-2}} \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

$$\Psi(\mathbf{r}) = \begin{cases} \Psi_{\text{bounded}}(\mathbf{r}) = \exp\left(\sqrt{-\frac{2mV(\mathbf{r})\Gamma(n/2)}{\hbar^2(n-2)\sqrt{\pi^n}} \int_{\Omega} G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r}' - V(\mathbf{r}) \oint_{\partial\Omega} \frac{\ln^2(\Psi_{\Omega}(\mathbf{r}'))}{V_{\Omega}(\mathbf{r}')} \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')}{\partial \hat{N}_{\mathbf{r}'}} d\mathbf{r}'}\right) \\ \Psi_{\text{unbounded}}(\mathbf{r}) = \exp\left(\sqrt{-\frac{2mV(\mathbf{r})\Gamma(n/2)}{\hbar^2(n-2)\sqrt{\pi^n}} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{d\mathbf{r}'}{|\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}'|^{n-2}}}\right) \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

According to the first postulate of quantum mechanics, (15,18) are capable of modeling the time evolution of any wave function so long as they are normalized. Since there exist well-known PDEs which resemble Schrödinger equations but lack a quantum mechanical nature or application and therefore do not require normalization of their solutions, (15,18) may serve as general solutions for these PDEs. We now turn our attention to ensuring the normalization of (15,18) for quantum mechanical problems.

3.5 Normalization and the Born probability

With the wave functions (15,18) in hand, their probabilistic interpretations must be rendered maximally consistent with the mathematical definition of a probability distribution. More specifically, the Born probability, or the integral of the squared magnitude of (15,18) over a subset of $\Omega(t)$, must lie between zero and one [12]. Integration over all of $\Omega(t)$ must yield a Born probability of unity. Assurance of normalization by the satisfaction of both parts of the definition of the Born probability when working with (15,18) may be obtained through the use of a normalization parameter $N : \mathbb{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ chosen such that $\int_{\Omega} |\Psi_{\text{norm}}(\mathbf{r}, t)|^2 d\mathbf{r} = \int_{\Omega} |N(t)\Psi(\mathbf{r}, t)|^2 d\mathbf{r} = 1$. We now seek explicit expressions for N which produce normalized versions of the time-independent (18) and time-dependent (15) wave functions.

3.5.1 Normalizing the time-independent wave function

Because N must be a constant for (16) to hold when N is used (19) as a multiple of $\Psi(\mathbf{r})$, N may be factored out of the normalization integral and found explicitly (20) in terms of $\Psi(\mathbf{r})$. Substituting

(20) into the definition of N yields expressions (21) for both the bounded and unbounded normalized wave functions satisfying (16).

$$\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2(N\Psi(\mathbf{r})) = NV(\mathbf{r})\Psi(\mathbf{r}) \implies \frac{\partial N}{\partial \mathbf{r}} = 0 \implies N \in \mathbb{C} \quad (19)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} |N\Psi(\mathbf{r})|^2 d\mathbf{r} = 1 \implies N = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\int_{\Omega} |\Psi(\mathbf{r})|^2 d\mathbf{r}}} \quad (20)$$

$$\Psi_{\text{norm}}(\mathbf{r}) = \begin{cases} \Psi_{\text{norm,bounded}}(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{\exp\left(\sqrt{-\frac{2mV(\mathbf{r})\Gamma(n/2)}{\hbar^2(n-2)\sqrt{\pi^n}} \int_{\Omega} G(\mathbf{r},\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r}' - V(\mathbf{r}) \oint_{\partial\Omega} \frac{\ln^2(\Psi_{\Omega}(\mathbf{r}'))}{V_{\Omega}(\mathbf{r}')} \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{r},\mathbf{r}')}{\partial N_{\mathbf{r}'}} d\mathbf{r}'}\right)}{\sqrt{\int_{\Omega} \left| \exp\left(\sqrt{-\frac{2mV(\mathbf{r})\Gamma(n/2)}{\hbar^2(n-2)\sqrt{\pi^n}} \int_{\Omega} G(\mathbf{r},\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r}' - V(\mathbf{r}) \oint_{\partial\Omega} \frac{\ln^2(\Psi_{\Omega}(\mathbf{r}'))}{V_{\Omega}(\mathbf{r}')} \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{r},\mathbf{r}')}{\partial N_{\mathbf{r}'}} d\mathbf{r}'}\right)} \right|^2 d\mathbf{r}}} \\ \Psi_{\text{norm,unbounded}}(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{\exp\left(\sqrt{-\frac{2mV(\mathbf{r})\Gamma(n/2)}{\hbar^2(n-2)\sqrt{\pi^n}} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{d\mathbf{r}'}{|\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}'|^{n-2}}}\right)}{\sqrt{\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \left| \exp\left(\sqrt{-\frac{2mV(\mathbf{r})\Gamma(n/2)}{\hbar^2(n-2)\sqrt{\pi^n}} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{d\mathbf{r}'}{|\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}'|^{n-2}}}\right) \right|^2 d\mathbf{r}}} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

3.5.2 Normalizing the time-dependent wave function

Normalizing the time-dependent wave function is similar to that of its time-independent counterpart, with the exception that the derivation of N by (19) causes N to become a time-dependent quantity $N(t)$ in its own right due to the normalization integral being only over space. However, when the definition $\Psi_{\text{norm}}(\mathbf{r}, t) = N(t)\Psi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ of N is substituted into (1) as was done in (19), one is forced to again conclude that N must be constant. This apparent contradiction is resolved by observing three primary facts about the nature of (1). The first is that (1) assumes a normalized solution from the beginning, while the second is that the act of solving (1) does not automatically guarantee normalization. Rather, one must solve (1) and then proceed with normalization. The third fact is that the time-dependent potential term, together with boundary conditions if transient, is the force that causes the wave function to evolve through time. To guarantee that the system remains normalized at all times, the normalization parameter must evolve likewise through time. Intuitively speaking, a change in the wave function implies a change in the correction factor used to ensure normalization, and this reality is implicit in (1) but must be made explicit in its solution. Thus, the evidence falls in favor of a time-dependent N . Performing the same procedure as with (19) to derive N produces a time-dependent N , and multiplying this $N(t)$ by $\Psi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ yields the normalized time-dependent wave functions (22) for both bounded and unbounded domains.

$$\Psi_{\text{norm}}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l}
\Psi_{\text{norm,bounded}}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \exp \left(\left(\left(V(\mathbf{r}, t) \int_{\Omega(t)} \frac{\ln^2(\Psi_0(\mathbf{r}'))}{V_0(\mathbf{r}')} G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', t) d\mathbf{r}' \right. \right. \right. \\
- \frac{2V(\mathbf{r}, t)}{i\hbar} \int_0^t \int_{\Omega(t)} G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', t - \tau) d\mathbf{r}' d\tau \\
+ \left. \left. \left. \frac{i\hbar V(\mathbf{r}, t)}{2m} \int_0^t \oint_{\partial\Omega(t)} \frac{\ln^2(\Psi_\Omega(\mathbf{r}', \tau))}{V_\Omega(\mathbf{r}', \tau)} \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', t - \tau)}{\partial \hat{N}_{\mathbf{r}'}} d\mathbf{r}' d\tau \right)^{1/2} \right) \right) \\
\left(\left(\int_{\Omega(t)} \left| \exp \left(\left(V(\mathbf{r}, t) \int_{\Omega(t)} \frac{\ln^2(\Psi_0(\mathbf{r}'))}{V_0(\mathbf{r}')} G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', t) d\mathbf{r}' \right. \right. \right. \right. \right. \\
- \frac{2V(\mathbf{r}, t)}{i\hbar} \int_0^t \int_{\Omega(t)} G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', t - \tau) d\mathbf{r}' d\tau \\
+ \left. \left. \left. \frac{i\hbar V(\mathbf{r}, t)}{2m} \int_0^t \oint_{\partial\Omega(t)} \frac{\ln^2(\Psi_\Omega(\mathbf{r}', \tau))}{V_\Omega(\mathbf{r}', \tau)} \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', t - \tau)}{\partial \hat{N}_{\mathbf{r}'}} d\mathbf{r}' d\tau \right)^{1/2} \right) \right)^2 d\mathbf{r} \right)^{-1/2} \\
\Psi_{\text{norm,unbounded}}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \exp \left(\left(\left(\frac{2V(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\left(2\sqrt{\frac{\pi i\hbar t}{2m}}\right)^n} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{\ln^2(\Psi_0(\mathbf{r}'))}{2V_0(\mathbf{r}')} \exp\left(-\frac{m|\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}'|^2}{2i\hbar t}\right) d\mathbf{r}' \right. \right. \right. \\
+ \left. \left. \left. \frac{2V(\mathbf{r}, t)}{i\hbar} \int_0^t \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{m|\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}'|^2}{2i\hbar(t-\tau)}\right)}{\left(2\sqrt{\frac{\pi i\hbar(t-\tau)}{2m}}\right)^n} d\mathbf{r}' d\tau \right)^{1/2} \right) \right) \\
\left(\left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \left| \exp \left(\left(\frac{2V(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\left(2\sqrt{\frac{\pi i\hbar t}{2m}}\right)^n} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{\ln^2(\Psi_0(\mathbf{r}'))}{2V_0(\mathbf{r}')} \exp\left(-\frac{m|\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}'|^2}{2i\hbar t}\right) d\mathbf{r}' \right. \right. \right. \right. \right. \\
+ \left. \left. \left. \frac{2V(\mathbf{r}, t)}{i\hbar} \int_0^t \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{m|\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}'|^2}{2i\hbar(t-\tau)}\right)}{\left(2\sqrt{\frac{\pi i\hbar(t-\tau)}{2m}}\right)^n} d\mathbf{r}' d\tau \right)^{1/2} \right) \right)^2 d\mathbf{r} \right)^{-1/2}
\end{array} \right. \quad (22)$$

Since a normalized solution (22) to (1) adaptable to steady or unsteady systems on bounded or unbounded domains has been found, Claim 2 stands. The result is contained within Theorem 2.

Theorem 2 *If $g \in \{\Psi, V, \Phi\} : (\mathbf{r} \in \Omega(t) \times t \in \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, $\Psi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ satisfies the Schrödinger equation $i\hbar \frac{\partial \Psi(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} = V(\mathbf{r}, t)\Psi - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 \Psi(\mathbf{r}, t)$, and $\Phi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ satisfies the unit-forced heat equation $\frac{\partial \Phi(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} = 1 + \nabla^2 \Phi(\mathbf{r}, t)$, then the invertible change of variables $\Psi(\mathbf{r}, t) = \exp\left(\sqrt{\frac{2\Phi(\mathbf{r}, t)V(\mathbf{r}, t)}{i\hbar}}\right)$ transforms the Schrödinger equation into the unit-forced heat equation such that $\Psi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ may be recovered from $\Phi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ provided that there exist sufficiently smooth boundary conditions $g_\Omega : (\mathbf{r} \in \partial\Omega(t) \times t \in \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, initial conditions $g_0 : \mathbf{r} \in \Omega(0) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, and a normalization condition $N : t \in \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{C} = \left(\int_{\Omega(t)} |\Psi(\mathbf{r}, t)|^2 d\mathbf{r}\right)^{-1/2}$.*

4 Practical applications

The general and analytical solutions (15, 18, 21-22) to (1,16) may be applied to the analysis of many practical scenarios in theoretical physics, chemistry, engineering, and mathematics. We consider two applications in this work. The first is the derivation of closed-form wave functions of atomic orbitals (23-33) and the second is solving the viscous one-dimensional Burgers equation (34-40) with a spatiotemporally variable forcing term by reduction to a real-valued version of (1).

4.1 Application to atomic orbitals

Deriving the probability of locating an electron in the electron cloud surrounding an atomic nucleus is of great interest in quantum chemistry and is considered a classic example of a problem in quantum mechanics. Its exact solution is only known for the lone electron of a hydrogen atom. The solution has been extended to account for higher energy levels of the electron, which collectively form so-called "hydrogen-like atoms." However, the wave function of a helium atom (or any heavier atom) remains unknown due to the presence of a term accounting for the repulsive force between multiple electrons. The mathematical makeup of this term is such that the mathematical technique of separation of variables cannot be employed to derive the wave function as with hydrogen. But when the transformation (16-18) is applied to reduce the time-independent Schrödinger equation to a Poisson equation, the potential term is temporarily eliminated. The method of separation of variables can then be used to solve the Poisson equation, enabling the helium wave function to be recovered by reversing the transformation of (16-18) and choosing an appropriate constant multiple to ensure normalization per (21). Since this method temporarily eliminates the potential for all n , the theory may be extended to yield the wave function of any atom.

4.1.1 Coordinate definitions

We first define the multidimensional Laplacian operator notation in spherical coordinates as (23).

$$\nabla_n^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{r_i^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r_i} \left(r_i^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r_i} \right) + \frac{1}{r_i^2 \sin(\theta_i)} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_i} \left(\sin(\theta_i) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_i} \right) + \frac{1}{r_i^2 \sin^2(\theta_i)} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi_i^2} \right) \quad (23)$$

4.1.2 The helium atom with static-nucleus approximation

The Schrödinger equation for the helium atom [13] is given by (24) where $\mathbf{r}_1$ and $\mathbf{r}_2$ are the distances between the nucleus and the two electrons respectively, e is the elementary charge, ϵ_0 is the permittivity of free space, $\mu = \frac{m_n m_e}{m_n + m_e}$ is the reduced mass of either electron m_e with respect to the nucleus m_n , and E is the total energy of the system. The boundary conditions are the same as those of the hydrogen atom, namely $\lim_{\mathbf{r} \rightarrow \infty} \Psi(\mathbf{r}) = 0$ and $\lim_{\mathbf{r} \rightarrow 0} \Psi(\mathbf{r}) \in \mathbb{C}$.

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{1}{r_1^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r_1} \left(r_1^2 \frac{\partial \Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2)}{\partial r_1} \right) + \frac{1}{r_1^2 \sin(\theta_1)} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_1} \left(\sin(\theta_1) \frac{\partial \Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2)}{\partial \theta_1} \right) + \frac{1}{r_1^2 \sin^2(\theta_1)} \frac{\partial^2 \Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2)}{\partial \phi_1^2} \right) \\ & + \frac{1}{r_2^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r_2} \left(r_2^2 \frac{\partial \Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2)}{\partial r_2} \right) + \frac{1}{r_2^2 \sin(\theta_2)} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_2} \left(\sin(\theta_2) \frac{\partial \Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2)}{\partial \theta_2} \right) + \frac{1}{r_2^2 \sin^2(\theta_2)} \frac{\partial^2 \Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2)}{\partial \phi_2^2} \Big) \\ & + \frac{2\mu}{m_n} \left(\frac{\partial \Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2)}{\partial r_1} \frac{\partial \Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2)}{\partial r_2} + \frac{1}{r_1 r_2} \frac{\partial \Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2)}{\partial \theta_1} \frac{\partial \Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2)}{\partial \theta_2} \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \frac{1}{r_1 r_2 \sin(\theta_1) \sin(\theta_2)} \frac{\partial \Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2)}{\partial \phi_1} \frac{\partial \Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2)}{\partial \phi_2} \right) \\ & = \left(\frac{e^2 \mu}{2\pi \epsilon_0 \hbar^2} \left(\frac{1}{|\mathbf{r}_1 - \mathbf{r}_2|} - \frac{2}{|\mathbf{r}_1|} - \frac{2}{|\mathbf{r}_2|} \right) - \frac{2\mu E}{\hbar^2} \right) \Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2) \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

Approximating the system barycenter as located at the center of the nucleus requires that $m_n \rightarrow \infty$ and consequently $\mu \rightarrow m_e$. All first-order partial derivatives of the wave function thus cancel. The Schrödinger equation for the helium atom (24) is now written in a form (25) compatible with Theorem 2.

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{1}{r_1^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r_1} \left(r_1^2 \frac{\partial \Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2)}{\partial r_1} \right) + \frac{1}{r_1^2 \sin(\theta_1)} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_1} \left(\sin(\theta_1) \frac{\partial \Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2)}{\partial \theta_1} \right) + \frac{1}{r_1^2 \sin^2(\theta_1)} \frac{\partial^2 \Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2)}{\partial \phi_1^2} \right) \\ & + \frac{1}{r_2^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r_2} \left(r_2^2 \frac{\partial \Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2)}{\partial r_2} \right) + \frac{1}{r_2^2 \sin(\theta_2)} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_2} \left(\sin(\theta_2) \frac{\partial \Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2)}{\partial \theta_2} \right) + \frac{1}{r_2^2 \sin^2(\theta_2)} \frac{\partial^2 \Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2)}{\partial \phi_2^2} \Big) \\ & = \left(\frac{e^2 \mu}{2\pi\epsilon_0 \hbar^2} \left(\frac{1}{|\mathbf{r}_1 - \mathbf{r}_2|} - \frac{2}{|\mathbf{r}_1|} - \frac{2}{|\mathbf{r}_2|} \right) - \frac{2\mu E}{\hbar^2} \right) \Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2) \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

Applying Theorem 2 by performing the transformation outlined in (16-19) maps (25) to a six-dimensional spherically coordinated Poisson equation (26).

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &= \frac{1}{r_1^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r_1} \left(r_1^2 \frac{\partial \Phi(\mathbf{r})}{\partial r_1} \right) + \frac{1}{r_1^2 \sin(\theta_1)} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_1} \left(\sin(\theta_1) \frac{\partial \Phi(\mathbf{r})}{\partial \theta_1} \right) + \frac{1}{r_1^2 \sin^2(\theta_1)} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi(\mathbf{r})}{\partial \phi_1^2} + \\ & \frac{1}{r_2^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r_2} \left(r_2^2 \frac{\partial \Phi(\mathbf{r})}{\partial r_2} \right) + \frac{1}{r_2^2 \sin(\theta_2)} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_2} \left(\sin(\theta_2) \frac{\partial \Phi(\mathbf{r})}{\partial \theta_2} \right) + \frac{1}{r_2^2 \sin^2(\theta_2)} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi(\mathbf{r})}{\partial \phi_2^2} \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

Since the two three-dimensional Laplacians of the wave function in (26) are taken with respect to the space coordinates of each electron and do not share any such coordinates, the Poisson equation defined on $\mathbb{R}^6$ may be separated into two Poisson equations (27-28) defined on $\mathbb{R}^3$ by decomposing the caloric function into a sum $\Phi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2) = \Phi_1(\mathbf{r}_1) + \Phi_2(\mathbf{r}_2)$ of two functions that satisfy the separated Poisson equations. The quantity λ is the constant of separation, and the condition $0 < \lambda < 1$ is imposed to prevent loss of generality by a reduction of (27-28) to Laplace equations.

$$\alpha_1 = 1 - \lambda = \frac{1}{r_1^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r_1} \left(r_1^2 \frac{\partial \Phi_1(\mathbf{r})}{\partial r_1} \right) + \frac{1}{r_1^2 \sin(\theta_1)} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_1} \left(\sin(\theta_1) \frac{\partial \Phi_1(\mathbf{r})}{\partial \theta_1} \right) + \frac{1}{r_1^2 \sin^2(\theta_1)} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi_1(\mathbf{r})}{\partial \phi_1^2} \quad (27)$$

$$\alpha_2 = \lambda = \frac{1}{r_2^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r_2} \left(r_2^2 \frac{\partial \Phi_2(\mathbf{r})}{\partial r_2} \right) + \frac{1}{r_2^2 \sin(\theta_2)} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_2} \left(\sin(\theta_2) \frac{\partial \Phi_2(\mathbf{r})}{\partial \theta_2} \right) + \frac{1}{r_2^2 \sin^2(\theta_2)} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi_2(\mathbf{r})}{\partial \phi_2^2} \quad (28)$$

Separating variables once more and imposing the boundary conditions $\lim_{\mathbf{r} \rightarrow \infty} \Psi(\mathbf{r}) = 0 \wedge \lim_{\mathbf{r} \rightarrow 0} \Psi(\mathbf{r}) \in \mathbb{C}$ results in the solutions (29-30) to (27-28), where Y_b^a is the spherical harmonic of a th order and b th degree [14]. While their sum (31) forms a fairly general solution of (26), the principal quantum numbers n_1 and n_2 must also be found. Since there exists one arbitrary constant $C_i | i \in \{1, 2\}$ per separated solution, each constant is understood to depend on the respective principal quantum number. The quantities ℓ_1 and ℓ_2 are the azimuthal quantum numbers of the first and second electrons respectively while m_1 and m_2 are their magnetic quantum numbers. Since wave functions per (1,16) are not generally understood to include the effects of spin quantum numbers, a detailed spinor analysis of the singlet and triplet states is outside the scope of this work.

$$\Phi_1(\mathbf{r}_1) = \sum_{\ell_1=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m_1=-\ell_1}^{\ell_1} \left(C_1(n_1)r_1^{\ell_1} - \frac{\alpha_1 r_1^2}{4 - \ell_1(\ell_1 - 1)} \right) Y_{\ell_1}^{m_1}(\theta_1, \phi_1) \quad (29)$$

$$\Phi_2(\mathbf{r}_2) = \sum_{\ell_2=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m_2=-\ell_2}^{\ell_2} \left(C_2(n_2)r_2^{\ell_2} - \frac{\alpha_2 r_2^2}{4 - \ell_2(\ell_2 - 1)} \right) Y_{\ell_2}^{m_2}(\theta_2, \phi_2) \quad (30)$$

$$\Phi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2) = \sum_{k=1}^2 \sum_{\ell_k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m_k=-\ell_k}^{\ell_k} \left(C_k(n_k)r_k^{\ell_k} - \frac{\alpha_k r_k^2}{4 - \ell_k(\ell_k - 1)} \right) Y_{\ell_k}^{m_k}(\theta_k, \phi_k) \quad (31)$$

Reversing the change of variables in Theorem 2 which culminates in (21) allows the wave function to be recovered (32) in terms of the Poisson equation sum solution (31) where $\Xi = n_1, n_2, \ell_1, \ell_2, m_1, m_2$. While the wave function appears complete sans a deterministic expression for the electronic position vectors, it remains necessary to choose coefficients C_1 and C_2 such that the wave function is quantized according to the principal quantum numbers n_1 and n_2 . The physical interpretation of λ is uncertain, however it may play a part in providing assurance of quantization.

$$\Psi_{\Xi}(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2) = \frac{\exp \left(\sqrt{-\frac{2 \sum_{k=1}^2 \sum_{\ell_k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m_k=-\ell_k}^{\ell_k} \left(C_k(n_k)r_k^{\ell_k} - \frac{\alpha_k r_k^2}{4 - \ell_k(\ell_k - 1)} \right) Y_{\ell_k}^{m_k}(\theta_k, \phi_k)}{\left(\frac{e^2 \mu}{2\pi\epsilon_0 \hbar^2} \left(\frac{1}{|\mathbf{r}_1 - \mathbf{r}_2|} - \frac{2}{|\mathbf{r}_1|} - \frac{2}{|\mathbf{r}_2|} \right) - \frac{2\mu E}{\hbar^2} \right)^{-1}}} \right)}{\sqrt{\int_{\mathbb{R}^6} \left| \exp \left(\sqrt{-\frac{2 \sum_{k=1}^2 \sum_{\ell_k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m_k=-\ell_k}^{\ell_k} \left(C_k(n_k)r_k^{\ell_k} - \frac{\alpha_k r_k^2}{4 - \ell_k(\ell_k - 1)} \right) Y_{\ell_k}^{m_k}(\theta_k, \phi_k)}{\left(\frac{e^2 \mu}{2\pi\epsilon_0 \hbar^2} \left(\frac{1}{|\mathbf{r}_1 - \mathbf{r}_2|} - \frac{2}{|\mathbf{r}_1|} - \frac{2}{|\mathbf{r}_2|} \right) - \frac{2\mu E}{\hbar^2} \right)^{-1}}} \right) \right|^2 d\mathbf{r}_1 d\mathbf{r}_2}} \quad (32)$$

4.1.3 Extension to an arbitrary atom and general multiparticulate systems

Since the transformation (16-18) applied to (25) yielding (26) renders this diparticulate system separable, and separability is not limited by the number of space dimensions needed to describe the system, this pathway to a solution for two particles may be extended to multiparticulate systems. For an atom with n_e electrons and Z protons whose barycenter is approximated as the center of its nucleus, the reasoning (25-32) for helium is applied to the multielectronic Schrödinger equation to yield the general framework of the wave function (33) where $\Xi = n_1, \dots, n_{n_e}, \ell_1, \dots, \ell_{n_e}, m_1, \dots, m_{n_e}$ and $\eta = (\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_{n_e})$. The solution to the time-independent Schrödinger equation is therefore shown to be adaptable to multiparticulate systems by reason of the separability of Poisson equations with constant forcing terms. Since constant-forced heat equations are likewise separable, this argument for the possibility of multiparticulate solutions is further extensible to time-dependent cases.

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=1}^{n_e} \nabla_k^2 \Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_{n_e}) &= \left(\frac{e^2 \mu}{2\pi\epsilon_0 \hbar^2} \left(\sum_{j,k=1, j \neq k}^{n_e} \frac{1}{|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_k|} - \sum_{k=1}^{n_e} \frac{Z}{|\mathbf{r}_k|} \right) - \frac{2\mu E}{\hbar^2} \right) \Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_{n_e}) \implies \\ \{\alpha_1 &= \nabla_1^2 \Phi_1(\mathbf{r}_1), \alpha_2 = \nabla_2^2 \Phi_2(\mathbf{r}_2), \dots, \alpha_{n_e} = \nabla_{n_e}^2 \Phi_{n_e}(\mathbf{r}_{n_e})\} \implies \\ \Phi(\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_{n_e}) &= \sum_{k=1}^{n_e} \sum_{\ell_k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m_k=-\ell_k}^{\ell_k} \left(C_k(n_k)r_k^{\ell_k} - \frac{\alpha_k r_k^2}{4 - \ell_k(\ell_k - 1)} \right) Y_{\ell_k}^{m_k}(\theta_k, \phi_k) \implies \end{aligned}$$

$$\Psi_{\Xi}(\eta) = \frac{\exp\left(\sqrt{-\frac{2\sum_{i=k}^{n_e}\sum_{\ell_k=0}^{\infty}\sum_{m_k=-\ell_k}^{\ell_k}\left(C_k(n_k)r_k^{\ell_k}-\frac{\alpha_k r_k^2}{4-\ell_k(\ell_k-1)}\right)Y_{\ell_k}^{m_k}(\theta_k,\phi_k)}{\left(\frac{e^2\mu}{2\pi\epsilon_0\hbar^2}\left(\sum_{j\neq k}^{n_e}\frac{1}{|\mathbf{r}_j-\mathbf{r}_k|}-\sum_{k=1}^{n_e}\frac{Z}{|\mathbf{r}_k|}\right)-\frac{2\mu E}{\hbar^2}\right)^{-1}}}\right)}{\sqrt{\int_{\mathbb{R}^{3n_e}}\left|\exp\left(\sqrt{-\frac{2\sum_{k=1}^{n_e}\sum_{\ell_k=0}^{\infty}\sum_{m_k=-\ell_k}^{\ell_k}\left(C_k(n_k)r_k^{\ell_k}-\frac{\alpha_k r_k^2}{4-\ell_k(\ell_k-1)}\right)Y_{\ell_k}^{m_k}(\theta_k,\phi_k)}{\left(\frac{e^2\mu}{2\pi\epsilon_0\hbar^2}\left(\sum_{j\neq k}^{n_e}\frac{1}{|\mathbf{r}_j-\mathbf{r}_k|}-\sum_{k=1}^{n_e}\frac{Z}{|\mathbf{r}_k|}\right)-\frac{2\mu E}{\hbar^2}\right)^{-1}}}\right)}\right|^2\prod_{k=1}^{n_e}d\mathbf{r}_k}} \quad (33)$$

4.2 Application to the forced Burgers equation

While the Cole-Hopf transform was famously applied to solve the viscous Burgers equation without a forcing term, a similar solution to the forced Burgers equation (34) remains a mystery in fluid mechanics. Exact solutions have been found for simplified cases such as $f(x, t) = f_1(x) + f_2(t)$, but perhaps the closest the literature comes to revealing $u(x, t)$ for arbitrary $f(x, t)$ has been by Lie group symmetry analyses, one of which was held back from finding a tractable formula for $u(x, t)$ by an encounter with the likewise unsolved Riccati equation [15] while another analysis remarked that the form of the solution is heavily dependent on the form of $f(x, t)$ [16]. Despite the difficulty of the forced Burgers and Riccati equations, there exists a well-known sequence of two changes of variables [17] [18] which converts (34) into a real-valued version of the Schrödinger equation. Since we have already solved the Schrödinger equation, the solution to (34) is derived likewise in this subsection. Since this fluid mechanical application does not directly deal with probability distributions, we use the unnormalized solution (15) to the time-dependent Schrödinger equation.

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + au\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = b\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + f(x, t) \quad (34)$$

Substituting $u(x, t) = \frac{\partial v(x, t)}{\partial x}$ into (34) and integrating the result with respect to x transforms the latter into the quadratic PDE (35).

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial t} - \frac{a}{2}\left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial x}\right)^2 = \int f(x, t)dx + g(t) + b\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} \quad (35)$$

Substituting $v(x, t) = \exp\left(\frac{aw(x, t)}{b}\right)$ into (35) transforms (35) into a real-valued unidimensional time-dependent Schrödinger equation (36).

$$\frac{\partial w}{\partial t} = w\left(\frac{b}{a}\int f(x, t)dx + g(t)\right) + b\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \quad (36)$$

Since we have reduced (34) to a Schrödinger equation (36), application of Theorem 2 to (36) yields a heat equation (37) with solution (38) for the domain $\Omega(t) = x \in \mathbb{R}_{[0, L]} \times t \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$, initial condition $\Phi(x, 0) = \Phi_0(x)$, and boundary conditions $\Phi(0, t) = \Phi_l(t)$ and $\Phi(L, t) = \Phi_u(t)$ [19].

$$\frac{\partial \Phi(x, t)}{\partial t} = 1 + b\frac{\partial^2 \Phi(x, t)}{\partial x^2} \quad (37)$$

$$\Phi(x, t) = \frac{2}{L}\int_0^L\Phi_0(x')\sum_{k=1}^{\infty}\sin\left(\frac{k\pi x}{L}\right)\sin\left(\frac{k\pi x'}{L}\right)\exp\left(-\frac{bk^2\pi^2 t}{L^2}\right)dx'$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \frac{2}{L} \int_0^t \int_0^L \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sin\left(\frac{k\pi x}{L}\right) \sin\left(\frac{k\pi x'}{L}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{bk^2\pi^2(t-\tau)}{L^2}\right) dx' d\tau \\
& + \frac{2\pi b}{L^2} \int_0^t \Phi_l(\tau) \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k \sin\left(\frac{k\pi x}{L}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{bk^2\pi^2(t-\tau)}{L^2}\right) d\tau \\
& - \frac{2\pi b}{L^2} \int_0^t \Phi_u(\tau) \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^k \sin\left(\frac{k\pi x}{L}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{bk^2\pi^2(t-\tau)}{L^2}\right) d\tau
\end{aligned} \tag{38}$$

The initial and boundary conditions of $u(x, t)$ are recovered (39) from those of $\Phi(x, t)$ by inverting the changes of variables that led (34) to (37), as is the velocity field (40). Substituting (39) into (38) and the result into (40) yields the exact and general solution of (34). It is important to note that the function $g(t)$ appearing as the potential term of (36) is not included in (39-40) because it carries no objective meaning in light of the inclusion of all initial and boundary data.

$$\begin{aligned}
\Phi_0(x) &= \frac{b \ln^2 \left(\int_0^x u_0(x') dx' \right)}{2a \left(\frac{b}{a} \int f_0(x) dx \right)}, & \Phi_l(t) &= \frac{b \ln^2 (u_l(t)x)}{2a \left(\frac{b}{a} \int f(x, t) dx|_{x=0} \right)}, \\
\Phi_u(t) &= \frac{b \ln^2 (u_u(t)x)}{2a \left(\frac{b}{a} \int f(x, t) dx|_{x=L} \right)}
\end{aligned} \tag{39}$$

$$u(x, t) = \frac{a}{b} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\sqrt{\frac{2b\Phi(x, t)}{a}} \int f(x, t) dx \right) \exp \left(\frac{a}{b} \sqrt{\frac{2b\Phi(x, t)}{a}} \int f(x, t) dx \right) \tag{40}$$

5 Conclusion

A general and analytical solution to the Schrödinger equation was found by adapting known and very broadly applicable methods for solving second-order PDEs to the peculiarities of the Schrödinger equation, especially the Riccati-Sturm-Liouville and modified Cole-Hopf transformations. Unlike its known solutions, which apply only to cases of simplified potential terms, this solution encapsulates cases of any and all potentials, whether they are functions of space, time, or both. Because its derivation process hinged on the linear differential operators of vector calculus, the solution can be extended to any number of space dimensions or particles. This shocking degree of generality allows a nearly complete theory of the helium atom to be derived, which is able to be generalized to describe any atom as well as a large variety of multiparticulate systems. Since the helium atom is the simplest system exhibiting quantum entanglement, the analytical study of quantum entanglement may now begin, as may that of higher orbitals of multielectronic atomic systems. In a second application, the solution to the Schrödinger equation was adapted to solve the forced Burgers equation of fluid mechanics, enabling progress toward a mathematical theory of the elusive phenomenon of turbulence. These results are expected to make significant progress toward a thorough analytical understanding of quantum systems and linear PDEs with variable coefficients more generally.

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